

Post-study questionnaire

* Indicates required question

1. Email *

2. 1. Moving forward, how much effort do you plan to spend on *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Not on my immediate agenda	Very little	Not as much as I want to	Moderate amount of effort	A lot
Optimizing pull request merge time	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Optimizing response time to issues	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Attracting a diverse group of contributors	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Retaining diverse contributors	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Fostering a connected community	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

Skip to question 3

In this study we are looking at diversity from the perspective of gender and affiliation

Gender diversity: refers to the representation and inclusion of individuals of different genders in various settings such as workplaces, communities, and organizations.

Affiliation diversity: refers to the inclusion of individuals from various organizations (ASF, Google, LinkedIn, etc), including those who are unaffiliated.

3. 2. Please rate your degree of agreement to the following statements *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
I am aware of the state of gender diversity in my project	☐				
I plan to take action to improve gender diversity in my project	☐				
I am aware of the state of affiliation diversity in my project	☐				
I plan to take action to improve affiliation diversity in my project	☐				
I am aware of the turnover trend within my project	☐				
I plan to take action to improve turnover within my project	☐				

4. 3. Please rate your degree of agreement to the following statements *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
This dashboard made me more aware of the diversity and inclusion within my project	☐				
This dashboard helped identify aspects to improve	☐				
This dashboard will not have an effect on my actions	☐				
This dashboard was useful to me	☐				
I would continue to use this dashboard	☐				

Usability questions

5. 4. Please rate your degree of agreement to the following statements *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
I think that I would like to use this dashboard frequently	☐				
I found the dashboard unnecessarily complex	☐				
I thought the dashboard was easy to use	☐				
I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this dashboard	☐				
I found the various functions in this dashboard were well integrated	☐				
I thought there was too much inconsistency in this dashboard	☐				
I would imagine that most people would learn to use this dashboard very quickly	☐				
I found the dashboard very cumbersome to use	☐				
I felt very confident using the dashboard	☐				

I needed to

learn a lot of things before I could get going with this dashboard

uas100010

You have reached the end of the survey, thank you for taking the time to participate

We value and appreciate your time. If you have any questions about the study, desire additional information, or wish to withdraw your participation, please contact me by email at guizanim@oregonstate.edu or anita.sarma@oregonstate.edu.

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